

Karanjin: isolation, structural characterization and its photophysical investigation in different solvents and micellar micro environments

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Abstract:

Karanjin (3-methoxy-2-phenylfuro [2,3-h] chromen-4-one), is a furanoflavone isolated from seeds of *Pongamia pinnata*, a legume well known for its traditional and pharmacological properties with an efficient remedy for human health problems. The present investigation deals with the development of novel methods for the isolation and characterization of Karanjin from the seed oil. Structural elucidation was carried out via HRMS, FTIR, XRD, NMR, Raman spectroscopy and thermogravimetric studies¹. Density functional theory (DFT) has also been used to calculate vibrational spectra of Karanjin with sufficiently high accuracy. In the present work, the spectroscopic properties such as UV-Visible absorption, steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence of Karanjin have also been investigated in SDS micelles and various solvents such as EtOAc, MeOH, and water as a function of the solvatochromic parameters². Molar extinction coefficients, oscillator strength, transition dipole moment, and Stokes shift of Karanjin are compared in SDS micelles and different solvents. Karanjin displayed significantly enhanced molar absorptivity and longer mean fluorescence lifetime in the presence of SDS micelles in comparison to pure water. The enhancement of Karanjin fluorescence in water-MeOH solvent mixtures revealed a bell-shaped pattern with an increase in water content. Karanjin fluorescence intensity decays in all the solvents were bi-exponential with decay times ranging from 1.3 to 3.4 ns. Karanjin in SDS showed the longest lifetime of 3.48 ns, possibly due to the restricted microenvironment inside SDS micelles. The mean lifetimes are highest in SDS and least in water. There is a significant improvement of photophysical property of Karanjin in micellar solution due to shielding from the water inside the micelle and inaccessibility of solvent molecule around the fluorophore molecule in surfactants. We hope that the photophysical characterization of Karanjin could provide initial insight into other potential applications in different areas.

Keywords:

Fluorescence, Furanoflavone, Karanjin, Micelles, *Pongamia pinnata*, Spectroscopy

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the SDS micellization in water encapsulating Karanjin, thereby enhancing the photophysical property of Karanjin.

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Advanced In Biomass And Biogas Energy

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Abstract:

There is strong scientific evidence that the average temperature of the earth's surface is rising and this may be attributed to increased concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂), and other greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere as released by burning fossil fuels. One of the chief sources of greenhouse gases is burning of fossil fuels. Biogas from biomass appears to have potential as an alternative energy source, which is potentially rich in biomass resources. In the present study, current literature is reviewed regarding the ecological, social, cultural and economic impacts of biogas technology. In this communication an attempt has been made to give an overview of present and future use of biomass as an industrial feedstock for production of fuels, chemicals and other materials. However, to be truly competitive in an open market situation, higher value products are required.

Keywords:

Biomass resources; biogas application; sustainable development; environment

Assessment Of Heavy Metals In Water, Fish And Sediments In Dams Around Mining Vicinities In Zamfara State, Nigeria.

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Abstract:

The concentrations of heavy metals in water, sediment and fish (*Tillapia Monsambicus*) in the three major dams in Zamfara State along gold mining vicinities were determined using standard methods for two years in 2014 and 2015 (four seasons). The concentration of heavy metals determined in water, sediment, and fish were generally high during the dry season with exception of Hg which recorded its highest concentration in year 2015. Zn and Cr levels in the water, sediment, and fish were within international safe limits while Cd (0.1022 mg/l), Pb (0.2104 mg/l) and Hg (1.8818 mg/l) levels were far above (0.01, 0.01 and 0.001mg/l) USEPA safe limits respectively for drinking water. Two major indices such as contamination factor (CF) and pollution load index (PLI) were used for determining the contamination level of water, sediment, and fish samples. The result revealed a high contamination factor for Cd, Pb and Hg across all the six locations and a general overall pollution load across all the locations. Generally, the concentration of the analyzed heavy metals in mg/l for water and sediments was in the order of Hg > Pb > Cd > Cr > Zn. Correlation analysis showed a significant and positive relationship for Cd and Zn and Hg and Cr during the wet season and a significant positive at the ($p > 0.05$) relationship for Cr and Zn in the dry season. The pollution index value of the water samples across all the three dams indicated that there is need for immediate intervention to ameliorate pollution particularly in the dry season.

Keywords:

Dams, Heavy metals, sediments, fish and gold mining.

Assesment of Calcium and Iron Levels in selected Fruits and Vegetables available in Kano State, Northern Nigeria

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Abstract:

Mineral elements are of vital importance to both plants and animals including humans which are required in large or small quantities for a variety of different functions. The present study was conducted to determine the moisture contents and concentration levels of Calcium (Ca^{2+}) and Iron (Fe^{2+}) in three different fruits and vegetables widely consumed in Nigeria (namely; Mango, Pine-apple, Watermelon, Cabbage, Tomato and Spinach) which were obtained from the Yan-kaba market of Kano City. In each case, Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry was used for the experimental analysis. Based on the results obtained, the moisture contents of the samples investigated showed that watermelon had the highest mean moisture content of 95.1% and spinach possessed the least moisture content of 63.7 %. The highest concentration of Calcium was recorded in Spinach (15.10 mg/L), and the least concentration was recorded in cabbage (4.20 mg/L). The highest concentration of Iron was recorded in pineapple (2.20 mg/L), and the least concentration was found in mango (0.17 mg/L). Therefore, comparing the mineral contents revealed in this research with the Recommended Dietary Allowances (RDAs) limits, the results showed that regular consumption of such fruits and vegetables is essential for bone and immune system development, respectively.

Keywords:

Calcium, iron, fruits, vegetables, moisture contents

Studies towards the total synthesis of Linotrins and its evaluation against bacterial infections leading to Stroke

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Abstract:

Infections and stroke are linked through inflammation. Common viral and bacterial infections can increase the susceptibility to stroke by promoting inflammation, thrombosis and atherosclerosis.1 Reciprocally, stroke commonly leads to disruption of protective mechanisms against infection and induces a cascade of anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive reactions, which greatly increases the risk of infection that, in turn, complicated acute stroke in 30% of patients.

2. Recent investigation suggested a potential role of lipoxygenase derived lipid mediators in infectious diseases.3 Protectin DX (PDX), an omega-3 lipid metabolite derived from docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) has beneficial effects in infectious diseases: for instance, inhibition4-5 of influenza virus replication; increased survival in mouse model of sepsis6. In addition, α -linolenic acid (ALA) supplementation prevented mortality and cerebral damage in model of ischemic stroke.7 Its lipoxygenase metabolites, called linotrins, which possess a similar E,Z,E conjugated triene as PDX, may produce immunomodulation and reduced bacterial infections that are risk factors of stroke. Thus, the our project aims at evaluating the bioactivities of linotrins against bacterial infections and against brain inflammation. We have successfully validated a 15 step strategy yielding linotrin in milligram scale. The chemical synthesis features highly stereoselective hydrometalation reactions to build the three desired double bonds. A Suzuki cross-coupling reaction afforded the expected conjugated E,Z,E-triene from Pre cursors A and B with excellent retention of the stereochemistry. Preliminary biological experiments were performed in microglial cells using bacterial endotoxin lipopolysaccharide (LPS) as pro-inflammatory stimulus. Linotrin induced significant reduction of interleukins IL-1 β and IL-6, and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α). Interestingly, it reduced inflammation at lower concentration than ALA. Further in vitro investigation including evaluation of its protective effects on different cytokines and chemokines (especially on subsequent release of CCL2, known to be triggered by LPS) and LPS-challenged HT22 neuronal cells lines and/or cortical neuronal cells are under investigation.

Keywords:

Inflammation, infectious disease, Lipids, medicinal chemistry, Total Synthesis.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the synthrtic scheme for the total synthesis of linotrin.

References:

Esenwa et al., Nature Rev. Neurol., 2016, 12, 594. 2) Westendorp et. al., BMC Neurol. 2011, 11, 110. 3) Balas et al., Prog. Lipid Res., 2016, 1. 4) Morita et al., Cell, 2013, 112. 5) Imai, Biochim. Biophys. Acta, 2015, 496. 6) Xia et al., Sci. Reports 2017, 7, 99. 7) Blondeau, Biochimie, 2016, 49.

Overview of physio-chemical behaviors and mechanical properties of biomedical nano-materials

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Abstract:

Recent advancement in biomedical field has place very large emphasis on nano-cellular level applications where very precise yet robust analyses are needed for high quality research findings. Over the past years, key scientific instrument players spent tremendous efforts to develop and produce analytical instrumentations to fulfill the demands of biomedical research and industries. With broad range of analytical instrumentation and techniques available in the market, it poses a big challenge for researchers to identify the most suitable techniques to be used in their biomedical research. In this paper, contemporary techniques targeting at mechanical properties (surface characterization and tribology) and physio-chemical behaviors (small-angle x-ray scattering, x-ray diffraction, Fourier-transform infrared-spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy) are exemplified to provide an overview of biomedical materials characterization down to the atomic level.

Secondary metabolites from medicinally important weed: *Achyranthes aspera*

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Abstract:

Achyranthes Linn (Family: Amaranthaceae), a genus of stiff herbs, is distributed throughout the tropical and subtropical regions. *Achyranthes aspera*, an erect annual herb (0.3-0.9m in height) is distributed throughout India (upto1000m), Baluchi-stan, Ceylon, Tropical Asia, Africa, Australia and America. The plant possesses diuretic, purgative properties and act as an antidote against snakebite. Seeds are emetic and used against renal dropsy and hydrophobia. The plant extract is also used as abortifacient and contraceptive. Presence of ecdysterone in its roots causes insect molting activity. Literature survey revealed that triterpene glycosides, aliphatic compounds, steroids, fatty acids, alkaloids and betaine have been characterized from its different parts. The present investigation describes the isolation of three oleanolic acid glycosides from the seeds of and four steroidal triterpenes from the leaves, stem and roots of *Achyranthes aspera* collected from Dehra Dun. The structures of these compounds were elucidated as 3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-(glucopyranosyl uronic acid)-Oleanolic acid [A], 3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-(glucopyranosyl uronic acid)-Oleanolic acid-28-O-- β -D-glucopyranoside[B], 3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-(glucopyranosyl uronic acid)- Oleanolic acid-28-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside [C], Spinasterol [D], Stigmasterol [E], α -spinasterol acetate [F] on the basis of ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, 2D NMR, MS spectral data and β -sitosterol [G] by direct comparison with an authentic sample. The compounds A, C, D and E are reported for the first time in *Achyranthes* genus. The occurrence of compound A and C is being reported first time. Antioxidant potential of the isolated compounds was also assessed by different bioassays. The results will be discussed in detail during presentation.

Key words:

Secondary metabolites, *Achyranthes aspera*, amaranthaceae, triterpenoids

A Short Review: Pharmacotherapeutic Management Of Obesity

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Abstract:

Obesity is known as a chronic disease. Obesity is also known as global public health problem. The word 'global' means there is a study estimate that there are approximately 500 million obese people around the world. According to World Health Organization, BMI of obese people are more than 30 kg/m². Treatment of obesity is very important and need to be done to reduce population of obese people along with possibility that leads to death. Medication is one of the ways to treat obesity. Therefore, objective of this review to provide medication that can be used to lose weight with mechanism and side or adverse effect.

Keywords:

Obesity, Drug treatment, Side/ Adverse effect, Orlistat, Lorcaserin, Topiramate/ phentermine, Diethylpropion, Phentermine, Naltrexone/ Bupropion

Anesthesia: A Short Review

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Abstract:

Anesthesia was founded way back then with the uses of traditional remedies and techniques until the first anaesthetic agent was publically introduced to the world since then anaesthesia going through a revolutionary over the century contributing in the Medicinal world. There were several types of anaesthesia such as local, regional, and general anaesthesia. They were also stages of anaesthesia based on the dose given which is sedative, hypnosis, and anaesthesia and may lead to coma or death. This review paper is reviewing various types of anaesthetic, and their facts and find.

Keywords:

Anesthetics, anaesthesia, local anaesthesia, general anaesthesia, types of anaesthesia, stages of anaesthesia.

Pharmacological Management Of Parkinson Disease: A Short Review

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Abstract:

Parkinson disease (PD) is a common body neuron disorder. It is chronic progressive neurological disorder identified by bradykinesia, tremor, fluctuation, rigidity and postural abnormal. The disorder may be connected with significant non-motor disturbances and also more commonly recognized motor complications. Most effective and widely uses levodopa as the precursor of dopamine, co-administered with carbidopa in the therapy of Parkinson disease. The adverse effect commonly occurs after a long duration of treatment. This review shows the drug treatment, facts and finding of Parkinson disease.

Keywords:

Parkinson's disease (PD)/ motor and non-motor complications/ diagnostic/ drug treatment/ levodopa carbidopa/ pharmacokinetic/ mechanism/ adverse effect.

A Short Review: Pharmacotherapeutic Management Of Epilepsy

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Abstract:

Epilepsy is a common neurological disorder, affecting more than 50 million people worldwide. Despite the availability of numerous antiepileptic drug, there remains a clinical need for novel and efficacious AEDs for use in 20-30% of patients in whom current drug therapy is either ineffective or associated with intolerable side effects.

Keywords:

Epilepsy, Neurological, AED, antiepileptic drug, side effects

A Systemic Review: Antioxidant Activity Of Medicinal Plants

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Abstract:

The medicinal plants are used in traditional treatments to cure variety of diseases many years. The aim of this study is to evaluate the phenolic contents and antioxidant capacity in the different plants extracting from the stems, roots, bark, leaves, fruits and seeds of several important medicinal species. In this present study, we identify how effectively these plants inhibit free radicals from damaging the cells. The assay methods that have been included in this review are; DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl), ABTS (2,2'-and-bis-3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) scavenging activity, FRAP (Ferric reducing antioxidant power), Superoxide radical scavenging, Hydroxyl radical antioxidant capacity (HORAC), Lipid peroxidation inhibition (LPO), Oxygen radical antioxidant capacity (ORAC) and Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity.

Keywords:

DPPH, ABTS, FRAP, HORAC, LPO, ORAC, Superoxide

Pharmacotherapeutic Of Multiple Sclerosis: A Short Review

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Abstract:

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic, often disabling disease that affects the central nervous system. The symptoms of having multiple sclerosis may be mild, such as numbness in the limbs, or severe such as paralysis or loss of vision. The progress, severity and certain symptoms of multiple sclerosis in any one person cannot yet be prognosticated. The treatment for multiple sclerosis is very much challenging with modifying the disease and by limiting the unwanted immune response. Individuals with MS are at higher risk for emotional disorders, which can notably destroy family, work, and social life. These mood disorders can be treated through a combination of psychiatric and psychological therapy and medication treatment.

Keywords:

Multiple sclerosis, central nervous system, paralysis, psychological therapy

Health Benefits And Medicinal Activity Of Cooking Oil: A Systemic Review

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Abstract:

Cooking oil consists of edible vegetable oils, olive oil obtained from olives, peanuts, and coconut oil, to name just a few of the many plants that are used. Populations in many regions began to process vegetable oils thousands of years ago, make use of whatever foodstuffs they had on hand to obtain oils for a difference of cooking purposes. Early peoples learned to use the sun, a fire, or an oven to heat oily plant products until the plants exuded oil that could then be collected. In this study, the medicinal activity of few commonly used cooking oil has been investigated.

Keywords:

Cooking Oil, vegetable oil, olive oil, medicinal activity

Medicinal Activity Of Commonly Used Cooking Herbs; A Review

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Abstract:

Since ancient times itself, herbs and spices serve purpose in cooking. The practice persevered until recent years. Including herbs and spices in food not only add flavour and enhance the taste but they possess high medicinal value. Powerful health benefits can be derived from them. However, to the utmost knowledge, there is no significant evidence that the paramount herbs and spices been used extensively across the country. They remain underutilized for their medicinal purpose and the reasons are unclear. The very commercial herbs like cinnamon, fenugreek, turmeric and black pepper are rich in source of antioxidants, exerts other important activities like antidiabetic, antihyperlipidemic, carminative and much more health effects(2). One herb serves more than one medicinal purpose and that's why they well assist in fighting against many diseases. The main objective of this study conducted is to determine the presence of the active compounds in 10 different herbs and spices that very commonly used among our people and their potent mechanisms for generating the beneficial health effects. This study has consequently aided to provide further details of the active compounds accountable for the herbs and spices important activities.

Keywords:

Cooking herbs, medicinal activity, diseases, active constituents

Mobile Phone Gaming Addiction And Management

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Abstract:

The use of videogames is a rapidly magnify phenomenon around the world that involves people of all age groups. The diversity of gaming platforms (e.g., dedicated console, personal computers, smartphones, tablets, and laptops) and the growth in demand have contributed to the gaming industry becoming one of the most profitable entertainment industries. However, there is evidence that when done in excess, video game playing can in some cases be addictive, especially online video game playing where the game never ends and has the potential to be a 24/7 activity. The American Psychiatric Association (APA) identify Internet gaming disorder as a new potential psychiatric disorder. In response to this gap in our understanding, the present study, a first for this research topic, estimate the period prevalence of this new potential psychiatric disorder using APA guidance, examine the validity of its propose indicators, evaluate reliability cross-culturally and across genders, compare it to gold-standard research on gambling addiction and problem gaming, and estimate its impact on physical, social, and mental health.

Keywords:

Gaming, addiction, behaviour

Survey Of Malaysian Consumer Probiotics

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Abstract:

In this globalization of the era, majority functional foods have become a strong relationship between diet and health. Nowadays, the most significant and regularly used functional foods compounds are probiotics. The fact about the using of probiotics microorganism to against and cure diversity of human ailment has been used for more than 100 years. Newly, there has been strengthening in research of probiotics which lead to an important of probiotics due to application on manufacturing products development and a beneficial effect in human health. From the perspective, probiotic microorganism has been extensively used to yoghurts and other fermented milk which are main products of functional foods comprising about 65% of the world functional food market. Moreover, probiotics have influence on local and systemic immune system, enhance lactose intolerance symptoms, stimulates toxin elimination and there are lot of beneficial effects that are not intervened by intestinal microbiota. This review summarizes the probiotics may have roles played in diet and health in order to investigate benefits of probiotics microorganisms.

Keywords:

Probiotics, Yogurts

A Systemic Review: Malaysia Traditional Herbal

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Abstract:

Traditional herbs are from a nature that has many benefits for human health. In Malaysia, there are many types of species of traditional herbs that can be as a lead compound into the modern medicines. This is because traditional herbs have many phytochemical compound such as flavonoid, saponin, amides, alkaloids, terpenoids and etc that can be applied in pharmaceutical areas and have many medicinal activities such as anticancer activity, anti-diabetic activity, anti-inflammatory activity, analgesic activity, antioxidant activity, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity, pro-fertility activity, hepatoprotective activity and so on.

Keywords:

Malaysia traditional herbal, traditional herbal, Phytochemical, medicinal activity.

Medicinal Activity Of Zingiber Officinale A Systemic Review

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Abstract:

Zingiber Officinale or commonly known by population as ginger has been used in cooking and drinks daily and also as traditional treatment among the old folk. Nowadays researchers throughout the world have conducted various activity on the ginger to prove that ginger had the potential to treat diseases such as nausea vomiting, anti-cancer, anti-bacteria, et cetera.

Keywords:

Zingiber officinale, ginger, disease, nausea, vomiting, bacteria, cancer

A Review Of Natural & Synthetic Color Use In Food Preparation

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Abstract:

Food colour is added to enhance the quality perception of the food. People perception is usually influenced by the appearance of the food and this indicates the flavour. Colour is of two categories natural colour and artificial colour. Natural Color is extracted from the plants or animal source. So they are quite expensive and not available in large quantity and then for the synthetic colour are petroleum-based products and constitutes aromatic rings. Colour is extensively used in food items like candies, bakery, confectionery, drinks, rice, and cooked as well as processed foods. Despite its extensive use the ill- health situations caused by over-dosed use of colour must not be under looked. Multiple disorders are related to the toxicity of artificial colour. Colour is potential to mutagenic either directly or indirectly.

Medicinal Use Of Green Tea: Review

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Abstract:

Green tea is made from *Camellia Sinensis* Theaceae plant leaves and is considered to have anti-cancer, anti-microbial, anti-oxidant and anti-diabetic properties. Many of the benefits of green tea are associated with (-)-epigallocatechin galatte (EGCG), a major component of green tea catechins.

Therapeutic Efficacies Of Honey: A Review

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Abstract:

The valuable impacts of honey on human wellbeing have for quite some time been perceived. Today huge numbers of those beneficial outcomes have been concentrated to explain its method of activity. This review quickly outlines the best-considered highlights of honey, featuring it as an engaging elective drug.

Plant Toxin: Review

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Abstract:

The plant that when touched or ingested in sufficient quantity can be harmful or fatal to an organism or any plant capable evoking a toxic and fatal reaction. This review gives an outline on different plant toxins, their toxin effect and different poisonous parts due to plant toxins.

Keyword:

Plant toxin, toxin effect, poisonous part

Medicinal Activity of Momordica Charantia Plant: Review

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Abstract:

Momordica charantia L. (*M. charantia*), a member of the Cucurbitaceae family, is widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. It has been used in folk medicine for the treatment of diabetes mellitus, and its fruit has been used as a vegetable for thousands of years. Various biological activities of *M. charantia* have been reported, such as anti-hyperglycemic, antibacterial, antiviral, antitumor, immunomodulation, antioxidant, antidiabetic, antiulcer, antifertility, anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities. This review addresses the chemical constituents of *M. charantia* and discusses their pharmacological activities

Keywords:

Chemical components, *Momordica charantia*, biological activities.

Medicinal Activity And Aloe Plants. A Short Review

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Abstract:

Chemical investigation of the leaves of Aloe Vera, Aloe Berhana, Aloe Rivae, Aloe Megalacantha, Aloe Pulcherima, Aloe Dorortheae, Aloe Polyphylla, Aloe Barbadensis Miller, Aloe arborescens, Aloe saponaria resulted in b-sitosterol, aloe-emodin, aloechryson, protocatechulic acid, berbaloin, aloinoside, nataloin and 7-hydroxy barbaloin. The results presented in this study indicate that these species compare favourably with the well-known aloes of commerce.

Keywords:

Aloe plants, antimicrobial activities, antioxidant activities, antitumor activities.

Review of Plants Having Antiviral Activity

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Abstract:

Both human and animals, viruses are the main hazard of antiviral activity. It enters into living body and redirects body metabolism to produce large copies of their genome and proteins. Diseases which caused by those viruses are difficult to handle with the help of currently available antiviral activity. So, aim of the study was to explore the plants toward antiviral activity, to get more understanding on better control of these viruses. Herpes virus, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), influenza, hepatitis virus were at top among all discovered viruses. Nowadays, it becomes demand for novel drugs to prevent those infections and the emergence from mutation of viruses. Rising incidence of resistance towards synthetic drugs and slightly rising costs on medicines it is well-timed to search for natural products such as natural plant-derived on antiviral drugs to reduce the resistance of viruses. Prominent modes of action against these viruses were inhibited by the potential antiviral agents for future drugs development. Some plants like *Allium sativum*, *Daucus maritimus*, *Helichrysum arenites*, *Pterocaulon sphacelate* and *Quillaja saponaria* emerged to have broad-spectrum antiviral activity.

Keywords:

Viruses, Herpes virus, HIV, hepatitis, Influenza, antiviral agent

“On water” palladium catalyzed directed arylation of 1H-indazole

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Abstract:

Recently, substantial “green-oriented” efforts have been achieved in the field of C-H activation through the development of “on water” transition metal-catalyzed reactions that allow economical, environmental and safety advantages. Also, it is disclosed that on aqueous conditions, the heterogeneous mixture of substrates and catalyst can be very effective for direct arylation under mild conditions.

Based on these facts, we are aiming to develop a new C-H direct arylation of 1H-indazole by using water as a green solvent in lower temperatures. Even though, the C3 direct arylation of 1H-indazole has been a significant challenge due to the lack of the reactivity at this position.

This communication describes the development of a versatile catalytic system based on palladium acetate/triphenylphosphine for a C-H arylation exclusively in water as a sustainable solvent. This new protocol furnished improved building blocks of arylated 1H-Indazoles on position C-3.

Keywords:

Indazole, arylation, green chemistry, C-H functionalization, cross-coupling.

Figure 1: Pd-catalyzed C-H arylation of 1H-indazole derivatives on water.

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